

**DETERMINATION OF PH IN FOODS WITH AN IONOMETER
PXSJ-216F****Sapaev Bayramdurdi¹****Saitkulov Foziljon Ergashevich²****Bo'riyeva Manzura Shuxratjon qizi³****Abduvaliyev Alisher Ma'rufjon o'g'li⁴****Usmanova Ayakoz Maxadulla qizi⁵**¹⁻²Tashkent State Agrarian University³⁻⁴⁻⁵Student of Tashkent State Agrarian University<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7450939>

Annotation: In the following scientific article, methods of determination of pH value of sausages using an ionometer are shown, and the importance of heavy metals is shown. Some of these heavy metals, the so-called trace elements - chromium, iron, cobalt, copper, manganese, zinc and tin in low concentrations are important for the human body, as they are necessary for metabolism. However, at higher concentrations, they are toxic and harmful to humans.

Key words: microelements, chromium, iron, cobalt, copper, manganese, zinc, lead, toxic, heavy metals, pH value, ionometer.

INTRODUCTION

Heavy metals such as cadmium, chromium and lead are natural components of the earth's crust and are commonly found in the environment in varying concentrations. They enter the human body through food, drink and air. Some of these heavy metals, the so-called trace elements - chromium, iron, cobalt, copper, manganese, zinc and tin in low concentrations are important for the human body, as they are necessary for metabolism. However, at higher concentrations, they are toxic and harmful to humans. Heavy metal poisoning can be caused by contaminated drinking water, air with industrial emissions, or contaminated food.

The eight trace elements most important in food hygiene control are mercury, cadmium, lead, arsenic, zinc, copper, tin and iron. 7 more elements are subject to control: antimony, nickel, selenium, chromium, aluminum, fluorine, iodine, and others if indicated. Mercury, cadmium, lead and arsenic are especially toxic. These elements have strongly pronounced toxicological properties even at the lowest concentrations, and hygienic requirements for the permissible level of the content of these toxic elements are imposed on all types of food raw materials and food products.

METHODS AND RESULTS

The sausage product weighing 10.00 g was boiled in 150 ml of deionized water for 1 hour, the volume of the solution was brought to 50 ml by boiling, filtered,

and then deionized to the mark in a 50 ml volumetric flask. It was filtered and the ion content and pH value were measured in a PXSJ-216F ion meter.

Conclusion

For boiled sausages, the pH value should be 6.5. Any deviation from this value will result in some of the moisture not being retained. Acceptable pH values of the finished minced meat are 6.0 - 6.8. A pH value of 6.5 or higher can be achieved with the help of phosphates. We carried out pH measurements using the ionametra pH probe of the digital laboratory.

References:

1. Saitkulov F. E. et al. 2, 3-Dimethylquinazolin-4 (3H)-one //Acta Crystallographica Section E: Structure Reports Online. – 2014. – T. 70. – №. 7. – C. o788-o788.
2. Saitkulov F. et al. TITRIMETRIC ANALYSIS OF CALCIUM CATION IN" MEGATON" VARIETY OF CABBAGE //International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 10. – C. 134-135.
3. Sapaev B. et al. Synthesis of 2-methylquinazoline-4-thione with the purpose of alkylation of 3-propyl 2-methylquinazoline-4-thione with alkylating agents //AIP Conference Proceedings. – AIP Publishing LLC, 2022. – T. 2432. – №. 1. – C. 020009.
4. Boymuratova G. O. et al. To Examine the Processes of Biochemical Action Of 6-Benzylaminopurine with Cobalt-II Nitrate Dihydrate on the "Morus Alba" Variety of Moraceae Plant //Eurasian Journal of Physics, Chemistry and Mathematics. – 2022. – T. 3. – C. 39-42.
5. Sapaev B. et al. Study of methylation reactions of 2-phenylquinazoline-4-tion with "soft" and "hard" methylation agents and determination of its biological activity //E3S Web of Conferences. – EDP Sciences, 2021. – T. 258. – C. 04023.
6. Saitkulov F. et al. Biochemical nutrition family plant rute-lemon leaved //Академические исследования в современной науке. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 17. – С. 268-273.
7. Usmonovich E. T., Bakhtiyor O'g'li A. S. Study of the Condensation Reaction of Amines Different Environment //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF BIOLOGICAL ENGINEERING AND AGRICULTURE. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 5. – С. 121-123.
8. Ergashevich S. F. et al. Photochemical Processes Photosynthesis Pathway On House Plants Leaves" Black Prince" //Texas Journal of Agriculture and Biological Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 10. – С. 76-78.
9. Ergashevich S. F. et al. Photochemical Processes Photosynthesis Pathway On House Plants Leaves" Black Prince" //Texas Journal of Agriculture and Biological Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 10. – С. 76-78.

10. Saitkulov F. et al. CHEMICAL FEEDING METHOD OF LEMON PLANT USING LEAF STOMATA //Академические исследования в современной науке. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 17. – С. 274-277.
11. Hugo P. Kortschak, Constance E. Hartt, George O. Burr. Carbon Dioxide Fixation in Sugarcane Leaves // Plant Physiology. - American Society of Plant Biologists, 1965. - March (vol. 40, no. 2). - P. 209-213.
12. Ф.Э. Саиткулов, Б.Ж. Элмурадов. Влияние природы метилирующего агента и растворителя на направления реакции метилирования 2н (метил-, -фенил-, -п-нитрофенил) хиназолин-4-онов.2022/7/30
13. 2-метилхиназолин-4-тионни “юмшоқ” ва “қаттиқ” метиллаш агентлари билан метиллаш. СамДУ илмий ахборотномаси 2015-йил,3-сон. Самарқанд 109- бет.
14. Ф.Э.Саиткулов, Захидов К,А., Самаров З.У., Синтез и изучение реакции метилирования хиназолин-4-тиона. Ўзбекистон республикаси фанлар Академияси журнали. № 4 2015 йил. С-54-56